

FREQUENCY OF ABO INCOMPATIBILITY IN NEONATAL JAUNDICE

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the frequency of ABO incompatibility in neonatal jaundice.

Methods:

This cross-sectional study included 156 patients and was conducted in the department of pediatrics at Dr. Faisal Masood Teaching Hospital Sargodha. We included neonates of age 1-28 days of either gender who were admitted with neonatal jaundice. Phototherapy was applied to all jaundiced neonates. The frequency of ABO incompatibility was noted. ABO blood incompatibility was labelled if the neonate had the presence of indirect hyperbilirubinemia with blood group type A or B and maternal blood type O.

Results:

The mean age at admission was 4.2 ± 3.5 days. The mean gestational age at birth was 38.4 ± 1.2 weeks, and the mean birth weight was 3172 ± 470 grams. Most of the neonates were from rural areas, with 106 (67.9%) residing in rural locations and 50 (32.1%) from urban areas. Out of 156 patients, ABO incompatibility was diagnosed in 19 (12.19%) patients.

Conclusion:

ABO incompatibility is common in neonates admitted with jaundice. Screening for blood group incompatibility between mother and fetus, along with timely intervention when ABO incompatibility is detected, can help decrease the risk of complications from neonatal jaundice.

INTRODUCTION:

Neonatal jaundice is a common condition seen in newborns and is a significant contributor to illness requiring hospitalization. It is estimated that jaundice leads to hospital admissions in approximately 10% to 35% of newborns.^{1, 2} During the first week of life, up to 80% of preterm infants and 60% of those born at term experience some degree of jaundice.³ Neonatal jaundice occurs when excess bilirubin accumulates in a newborn's blood, leading to a yellowish discoloration of the skin and eyes. The bilirubin threshold that produces visible jaundice can vary depending on the baby's skin pigmentation and the area examined. This yellowing often first appears in the eyes and then

spreads downward, reflecting a cephalocaudal progression. Jaundice in newborns can have either normal (physiological) or disease-related (pathological) origins.⁴ When conjugated (direct) bilirubin is elevated, underlying medical or surgical issues may be responsible. If left untreated, this can cause permanent liver injury.⁵ Serious complications of neonatal jaundice include brain damage (kernicterus) and potential links to neurodevelopmental disorders such as autism.⁶

ABO incompatibility is a notable cause of neonatal jaundice. In cases where a newborn has a different blood type from the mother—specifically, when the mother is blood group O and the infant is group A or B—maternal

antibodies can attack fetal red blood cells. This immune reaction triggers hemolysis, leading to early-onset jaundice, often within the first 24 hours of life. Unlike physiological jaundice, which typically appears between the second and fourth days after birth and resolves within a few weeks, jaundice due to ABO incompatibility is considered pathological because of its rapid onset.⁷ In rare cases, affected newborns may develop mild anemia. Furthermore, the hyperbilirubinemia associated with ABO incompatibility can be severe, sometimes exceeding 15 mg/dL. In contrast, physiological jaundice usually presents with lower bilirubin levels—less than 10 mg/dL in full-term infants and below 15 mg/dL in preterm infants.⁸

The aim of the present study was to determine the frequency of ABO incompatibility in neonatal jaundice.

METHODS:

This cross-sectional study included 156 patients and was conducted at the Department of Pediatrics at Dr. Faisal Masood Teaching Hospital Sargodha. The study was conducted from December 2024 to March 2025. We included neonates of age 1-28 days of either gender who were admitted with neonatal jaundice. Neonatal jaundice was diagnosed by the presence of the yellowish discoloration of the sclera or skin of the neonate and was labeled as pathologic if the total serum bilirubin rose above 5mg/dl per day or was higher than 12 mg/dl in term and higher than 15mg/dl in Pre-term neonates. Patients with co-morbid conditions such as sepsis, premature (gestational age <37 weeks), and low birth weight (birth weight <2500 grams) were excluded from analysis. Informed

consent was obtained from the parents of neonates.

Demographic data, including gestational age, gender, birth weight, residence, the father's profession, the mother's educational level, and the father's socioeconomic status, were noted. A complete history was taken, and a physical examination was done. Phototherapy was applied to all jaundiced neonates. The frequency of ABO incompatibility was noted. ABO blood incompatibility was labelled if the neonate had the presence of indirect hyperbilirubinemia with blood group type A or B and maternal blood type O.

RESULTS:

The baseline characteristics of the study population were as follows: The mean age at admission was 4.2±3.5 days. The mean gestational age at birth was 38.4±1.2 weeks, and the mean birth weight was 3172±470 grams. Most of the neonates were from rural areas, with 106 (67.9%) residing in rural locations and 50 (32.1%) from urban areas. Regarding the fathers' profession, 110 (70.5%) had jobs, 41 (26.3%) were involved in business, and 5 (3.2%) were unemployed. In terms of maternal education level, 15 (9.6%) were illiterate, 32 (20.5%) had primary education, 35 (22.4%) had secondary education, and 74 (47.4%) had matriculation or higher. With respect to socioeconomic status, 45 (28.8%) families were categorized as low socioeconomic status, 82 (52.6%) as middle, and 29 (18.6%) as high socioeconomic status (Table 1).

Out of 156 patients, ABO incompatibility was diagnosed in 19 (12.19%) patients (Figure 1).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

Age at admission (days)	4.2±3.5 days
Gestational Age at Birth (Weeks)	38.4±1.2
Birth weight (grams)	3172±470
Residence (%)	
Rural	106 (67.9%)
Urban	50 (32.1%)
Profession (%)	
Job	110 (70.5%)
Business	41 (26.3%)
Unemployed	05 (3.2%)
Education Level (%)	

Illiterate	15 (9.6%)
Primary education	32 (20.5%)
Secondary Education	35 (22.4%)
Matric and Above	74 (47.4%)
Socioeconomic Status (%)	
Low	45 (28.8%)
Middle	82 (52.6%)
High	29 (18.6%)

Figure 1. Frequency of ABO Incompatibility.

DISCUSSION:

Immune-mediated hemolytic diseases in fetuses and newborns occur when maternal IgG antibodies cross the placenta, targeting and destroying fetal red blood cells. Historically, these conditions were most commonly linked to incompatibility between the mother and fetus in the Rh(D) blood group system. However, the implementation of preventive measures has greatly decreased the occurrence of hemolytic disease caused by Rh(D) incompatibility.⁹

Immune-mediated hemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn occurs when maternal IgG antibodies cross the placenta and enter the fetal circulation, where they bind to fetal red blood cells and cause their destruction. Historically, the classic and most frequent form involved

feto-maternal blood group incompatibility in the Rhesus (Rh) D system. However, the widespread use of anti-D prophylaxis has led to a marked decline in the incidence of hemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn attributable to Rh(D) fetomaternal incompatibility.^{10, 11}

ABO incompatibility between mother and newborn usually leads to only mild hemolysis, and most affected infants experience a benign clinical course. This mildness is largely due to the fact that neonatal red blood cells have fewer A or B antigens on their surface. Nevertheless, there have been rare instances of severe hemolysis, including cases progressing to hydrops fetalis.¹²

With the successful prevention of Rh isoimmunization, ABO incompatibility is now

the leading cause of hemolytic disease in newborns.¹³ Among infants born at or after 35 weeks of gestation, ABO incompatibility is recognized as a primary risk factor for the development of severe hyperbilirubinemia.¹⁴ This condition arises specifically when a mother with blood type O gives birth to a child with either blood group A or B.¹⁵

In present study among the 156 neonates included in the study, ABO incompatibility was diagnosed in 12.18% neonates.

A study from Turkey identified ABO incompatibility as the underlying cause of neonatal jaundice in 9% of cases.¹¹

Another investigation carried out at Ayub Teaching Hospital in Abbottabad reported that 26.4% of infants diagnosed with neonatal jaundice had ABO incompatibility.¹⁶

For infants affected by ABO incompatibility, blood group O is the sole choice for exchange transfusion procedures. Ideally, Rh-compatible group O packed red blood cells suspended in plasma from either group O or AB donors (matching the baby's Rh type) should be utilized for transfusions.¹⁷

In short, jaundice in newborns caused by ABO incompatibility between mother and infant is still commonly encountered and represents the leading cause of erythrocyte incompatibility in neonates. While this condition is often mild, it can put infants at risk for severe hyperbilirubinemia and its serious complications, notably kernicterus. Prompt recognition of infants at higher risk for ABO incompatibility may help lower the rates of illness and death associated with jaundice and anemia.

CONCLUSION:

ABO incompatibility is common in neonates admitted with jaundice. Screening for blood group incompatibility between mother and fetus, along with timely intervention when ABO incompatibility is detected, can help decrease the risk of complications from neonatal jaundice.

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